

BATTERY2LIFE

Facts

Consortium: 11 Partners from 5 countries

Duration: 36 months (January 24-December 26)

Business Cases: Domestic storage in Austria and Industrial (grid-scale) storage in Greece

Funding: ~4M€

 info@battery2life-project.eu

 battery2life-project.eu

 [battery2life_eu](https://twitter.com/battery2life_eu)

 [BATTERY2LIFE Project](https://www.linkedin.com/company/battery2life-project)

In a nutshell

BATTERY2LIFE aims to facilitate the smooth transition of batteries to 2nd life use and boost the innovation of the European Battery Industry by providing enablers to implement open adaptable smart Battery Management Systems (BMS) and improved system designs towards reliable reconfiguration of used batteries.

Join our Stakeholders Group

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
**State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI**